

METHODS OF IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF TEACHING USING ICT IN EDUCATION

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Annotation: Information communication technologies (ICT) at present are influencing every aspect of human life. They are playing salient roles in work places, business, education, and entertainment. Moreover, many people recognize ICTs as catalysts for change; change in working conditions, handling and exchanging information, teaching methods, learning approaches, scientific research, and in accessing information communication technologies. In this digital era, ICT use in the classroom is important for giving students opportunities to learn and apply the required 21st century skills. ICT improves teaching and learning and its importance for teachers in performing their role of creators of pedagogical environments. ICT helps of a teacher to present his teaching attractively and able to learn for the learners at any level of educational programmes.

Key words: Communication, technologies, education, approaches, methods.

Importance of Education. An education is based on scientific humanism, which focuses on the use of technological and scientific advances to enhance the welfare of humans and democracy. Unlike many later statements, education for scientific humanism is worth reading because the emphasis is on individual control and benefits. The concepts of human capital and human resources render education primarily instrumental to economic prosperity. These concepts dehumanize people and place them in the same category as raw materials such as minerals. Education is supposed to solve the problems of knowledge-based economic growth, unemployment, reduction

of poverty and increasing inequality in wealthy, better health and alleviation of population pressures, more effective democracy and political stability, lower crime rates, sustainable environmental quality, and the social and personal disruption caused by constant technological change. All are vital aspects of true development. All are also fundamental to the quality of life for individual families and hence too human welfare. The proposed solutions are to:

- Building human capital by teaching skills that directly enhance productivity,
- Providing screening mechanism that identifies ability,
- Building social capital by instilling common norms of behavior,
- Providing a consumption good that is valued for its own sake.

Education is considered a part of a collaborative dynamic process to enable growth and development in support of a modern inclusive society . Education is a key driver in the creation of knowledge to accelerate diffusion and encourage innovation. Hence, education and training will have both direct effects in the market and indirect effects in the build up of research and development and implementation of innovation.

Educations and Globalisation. Globalisation provides a backdrop for analysing economic and social changes and concomitant changes in the education and learning sector. The globalizing education and learning economy are two most significant aspects of contemporary economic and social life. On the one hand, there is growing agreement that knowledge is now at the very core of economic welfare and development. On the other hand nations, regions, industries, and firms with a faster rate of growth are those, which more successfully manage to generate and apply knowledge. The crucial role of knowledge is now preached by a variety of academic, business, and policy sources. A global economy requires governments to develop a new approach, not only to trade fiscal policies but also structural policies. As the scope for state intervention in the economic sphere has become more and more constrained, policy makers have increasingly had to shift their attention to the ‘residual’ factors in the production function, principally technology and human capital. It is important to emphasize how the ‘education and learning’ economy and the ‘globalizing’ economy are strictly connected . It is obvious that knowledge and learning have always been a

crucial component in human systems. It is connected to the opening of new scientific discoveries and technological innovations. A circular process has taken place. On the one hand, the development of an integrated world economy has allowed the acquisition of information, expertise, and technology at a faster pace and often at lower costs than in the past. On the other hand, the current phase of globalisation has been nurtured by a generation of new technologies. The major technological advances of the last quarter of a century have in fact occurred in fields, which allow the production, communication, transmission, and storage of information. ICTs have, in other words, acted as the material devices to allow globalisation to occur. Finance, production, media, and fashion would not be as global as they are today without the generation of new technologies.

Benefits of using ICT in education. In our previous blog article we already talked about the clear benefits of e-learning platforms for education. However, this time we will focus on the advantages of ICT in general. It has been proven that the use of ICT in the classroom increases the motivation of the students, showing more interest and becoming more involved in the areas they study. ICT enables the use of innovative educational resources and the renewal of learning methods, establishing a more active collaboration of students and the simultaneous acquisition of technological knowledge.

Furthermore, ICTs are of great help in developing discernment. Being able to search for various sources and contrast them, as well as to structure information are some of the most notable skills that students develop thanks to the use of ICT. But there are more advantages:

1. Their interest in learning grows: the use of resources as varied as videos, websites, graphics, and games make traditional subjects more interesting. Multimedia content is a very useful tool to bring different subjects closer to students in a complete and entertaining way.
2. Interactivity: the use of ICT in the classroom promotes the student's active and participatory attitude, which is involved in learning and is positioned as the protagonist.

3. Collaboration between students: Collaboration between students is clearly enhanced thanks to various digital tools. It is much easier for them to create team projects, cooperate and learn from each other.

4. They enhance creativity: ICT tools stimulate the development of the imagination, as well as the initiative of all class members.

5. Increased communication: close communication between students and teachers is encouraged through various channels, in a more spontaneous and less formal way.

6. Personalization and content up-to-date: digital environments allow real-time updating of all information and resources. In addition, it is possible to adjust the tools and content to local and nearby realities.

The Importance of ICT in Education. Today we do not need to go any further than our own home or even room, to see some form of ICT in our lives. Whether it be a computer, plasma TV, or mobile phone, we all have them in some part of our lives. In today's society, people as consumers of ICT, all strive for the one dream – the dream of a connected life. This makes ICT a lifestyle choice for much of the population. In addition, this lifestyle choice is changing the way we communicate, increasing the rate of consumerism, and changing how we interact and gather information .

ICT has invaded and transformed many aspects of our lives to the extent that we live in an environment that is dominated by technology which itself is consumer-driven. No matter how we perceive its presence, there is no denying that it is an important part of our lives and that it is here to stay.

Key issues to remember in relation to the importance of ICT in Education are that:

1. E-learning or Online Learning: The presence of ICT in education allows for new ways of learning for students and teachers. E-learning or online learning is becoming increasingly popular and with various unprecedented events taking place in our lives, this does not only open opportunities for schools to ensure that students have access to curriculum materials whilst in the classroom but also allows them to ensure students outside the classroom such as at home or even in hospitals can learn.

2. ICT brings inclusion: The benefits of ICT in education is of such that students in the classroom can all learn from the curriculum material. Students with special needs are no longer at a disadvantage as they have access to essential material and special ICT tools can be used by students to make use of ICT for their own educational needs. Despite this, it opens up new issues related to the 'digital divide' and providing access to ICT tools and resources for those who are less fortunate.

3. ICT promotes higher-order thinking skills: One of the key skills for the 21st century which includes evaluating, planning, monitoring, and reflecting to name a few. The effective use of ICT in education demands skills such as explaining and justifying the use of ICT in producing solutions to problems. Students need to discuss, test, and conjecture the various strategies that they will use.

4. ICT enhances subject learning: It is well known these days that the use of ICT in education adds a lot of value to key learning areas like literacy and numeracy.

5. ICT use develops ICT literacy and ICT Capability: Both are 21st-century skills that are best developed whilst ICT remains transparent in the background of subject learning. The best way to develop ICT capability is to provide them with meaningful activities, embedded in purposeful subject-related contexts.

6. ICT use encourages collaboration: You just have to put a laptop, iPad or computer in the classroom to understand how this works. ICT naturally brings children together where they can talk and discuss what they are doing for their work and this in turn, opens up avenues for communication thus leading to language development.

7. ICT use motivates learning: Society's demands for new technology has not left out children and their needs. Children are fascinated with technology and it encourages and motivates them to learn in the classroom.

8. ICT in education improves engagement and knowledge retention: When ICT is integrated into lessons, students become more engaged in their work. This is because technology provides different opportunities to make it more fun and enjoyable in terms of teaching the same things in different ways. As a consequence of this increased engagement, it is said that they will be able to retain knowledge more effectively and efficiently.

9. ICT use allows for effective Differentiation Instruction with technology: We all learn differently at different rates and styles and technology provide opportunities for this to occur.

10. ICT integration is a key part of the national curriculum: The integration of digital technologies or ICT is a significant part of the Australian Curriculum for example, and this is a trend that many global governments are taking up as they begin to see the significance of ICT in education.

11. We live in a “knowledge economy”: This is an economy where it is vital to have the ability to produce and use information effectively. It is a time when ICT is pervasive and permeates throughout all industries in the economy whether it may be health, education, environment or manufacturing . The significance of ICT in the Australian economy was emphasised in the recent article by Alan Patterson, CEO of the Australian Computer Society, in his statement that the “ICT industry now rivals mining in terms of the contribution to the economy”

Conclusion: ICTs will continue to be a significant part of our future as it connects itself to more and more parts of our lives. It will continually evolve and change because as consumers we all like a choice. We like to use ICT for personal growth, creativity, and joy, consumption, and wealth.

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